

Correlation Context of Job Involvement and Organizational Culture

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ABSTRACT: The success of any organization depends on its culture, as it is invisible power governing the managerial processes. Organizational culture is the symbolic system of communication and connection in the organization including intangible linkages as beliefs, values, behavioral norms. It is the indivisible element of the organization in its unconscious set of programs, prescribing how to behave, act, communicate. Organizational culture is the sphere where managers deal with spirituality and leading values, attitudes. Work-related attitudes present an important managerial focus, they usually define work behaviors and actively influence productivity and overall employee performance levels. Managers perform within the “human-to-human” context, achieving effectiveness and efficiency of organization through and with other people. Human context makes human behavior important criteria for the company success. Job involvement in different interpretations can be viewed as psychological state, attitude, behavior. Some experts offer that job involvement is the level of psychological identification within the work or job. In other words, job involvement is the employee attitude on the place of the self in the work, like answering the questions, ‘how much I like myself doing this job’, ‘how much my identity finds comfort in this job’. The paper builds correlation areas of organizational culture and job involvement as important focuses in nowadays management.

KEYWORDS: organizational culture, job involvement, psychological identification with the job, correlation context

Introduction

In the year 2020, by the research data from LinkedIn Learning (T&P Theory and Practice 2020), the list of hard and soft skills shapes the important directions in development programs and managerial focus in organizations. The soft skills are presented by creativity, persuasion, collaboration, adaptability, and emotional intelligence (we cannot miss as well not long history of embodiment intelligence studies and concepts, like Mark Walsh research and projects (Embodied Facilitator Course 2020)). These skills prove the exaggerated focus on human dimension in organizational life and in business. The ideas of symbolic management, organizational culture power forces, and psychological states and attitudes like job involvement as identification with the work nature, again come to the limelight of organizational research.

Organizational culture

Organizational and individual aims and values alignment is a complicated process, but leading to organization’s effectiveness. Many times we do the values orientations exercise with our students, offering them to make a list of 10 values, and then to cross

some of them in different groups, and finally there are three values left. Then they need to work in small groups to offer the ways how managers can use organizational mechanisms to fit these individual values of their employees. Organizational culture is the context of these connections inside the company, it is widely regarded as the ‘humanizing’ component in business. It gives rise to an enabling atmosphere for airing mutual expectations between an employee and organization. This helps employees to trust each other, facilitate communication and develop organizational commitment. Culture can create a toxic or a healthy context for realization of human relationships in organizational life, and usually creates a strong framework for defining the spiritual frame of values organization stands for.

Organizational culture is determined by organization’s dominating values (Deal & Kennedy 1982) (Lauzen & Dozier 1994) accepted by the majority of employees (Wallack 1983) , as well as common norms and beliefs of organization’s member (Kroeber, Kluckhohn, Untereiner, & Meyer 1952) (Schein 1985; 1990) (Kotter & Heskett 1992) (Kotter 1996). Anthony Athos and Richard Pascale within the analytical framework of organizational effectiveness put shared values in the center, and assess organizational culture in the form of a philosophy that determines the ways organization would choose in its policy dealing with internal and external surroundings (Pascale & Athos 1981). Anja Krog (Krog 2014), citing Schneider (Schneider 2013) in the research, support the idea that most definition of organizational culture has a common denominator, - the idea of culture being something that is shared among organizational members. Within the systems approach in management, Fremont E. Kast and James E. Rosenzweig in the Academy of Management Journal paper “General Systems Theory: Applications for Organization and Management” (Kast & Rosenzweig, December, 1972) underline that the contemporary approach to systems emphasizes the multivariate nature of organizations and attempts to understand how organizations operate under varying conditions and in specific circumstances and ultimately directed toward suggesting organizational designs and managerial actions most appropriate for specific situations. Situation corresponds both to internal and external. In internal factors, following traditional vision of culture as consisting of the several layers (see Figure 1), and Edgar Shein’s (Schein 2004) organizational culture levels (see Figure 2), we can define the following: basic assumptions/values (like unconsciously accepted beliefs and values, moral principles, defining patterns), stated by management values/negotiated beliefs/norms of behavior, including ethical code (like what is important for our organization – e.g. fun, service, customers, happiness, profit etc.). They define behaviors and artifacts, - the visible expression of other elements, which usually become the focus of managerial analysis.

Figure 1. Culture Layers

Figure 2. Organizational Culture Levels by E. Shein

Organizational culture, including these elements, is based on the symbolic meanings defining humankind, like primary sense (see Figure 3), as Yuval Harari states in his book “Sapiens” (Harari 2015), Homo Sapiens is transcended the biological survival limits, breaking the laws of natural selection, and starting the laws of intelligent designs. It changes the laws of the workplace and the nature of job itself, where the realization of job identity becomes more important than simplistic material motivation. Job involvement as psychological state and attitude become significant in understanding the correlation context with organizational culture. Organizational culture has a significant influence on different elements of business, life and management in organization. People is an important element in understanding organization, along with structure and purpose, so human capital is the most dynamic and invaluable resource of a firm, understanding what employee behaviors and attitudes are affected by the organizational environment is critical (Krog 2014). Symbolic aspect of organization in the form of employee perceptions, attitudes, behavioral and communicative patters in the organizational environment are linked to numerous organizational results (House, Hanges, Javidan, & Dorfman 2004), and one of them is job involvement. Job involvement is more psychological characteristic of an employee, representing the level of intrinsic motivation and identification with the job responsibilities and meanings. Management is always interested in improving involvement levels in the work place, as high levels of employee involvement have been linked to greater success, productivity and strategic performance (Perrin 2003).

Figure 3. Organizational Culture Elements

Job Involvement

Job involvement is postulated as the measuring tool for the professional growth and it is how people see their jobs as both a relationship with the working environment, the

job itself and how their work and life are correlating. Aamir Ali Chughtai defines job involvement as the internalization of values about the work or the importance of work according to the individual (Chughtai 2008). Socialization of the employee is seen through the job involvement. An individual understands the values, abilities, behaviors, and social knowledge in dispensable for an organizational role through socialization and take part in as a member. Kanungo (Kanungo 1982) viewed job involvement as the cognitive state of psychological identification either in the context of a particular job, or with works in general. An individual's psychological identification with a particular job (or with work in general) in turn depends on the salience of his or her needs (both extrinsic and intrinsic) and the perceptions he or she has about the need- satisfying potentialities of the job (or work). In organizational behavior job involvement is understood as an attitude, the level of interest and commitment to the work tasks, however, it is important to differentiate it with job satisfaction, which stays for that the person is happy or satisfied with the job, with the responsibility for making the job correctly and following the organizational standards.

Job involvement is less important for the organizational effectiveness than job satisfaction, but is more important for the employee identity and organizational culture management. Involved employees find the connection of their values system with the organizational intangible relationships landmarks, as guiding symbols of the job, workplace, and individual differences correlation. Job involved staff have so much energy and they have enough enthusiasm to do their job tasks. M.Rama Kumari and V.Lakshmi Prasanna Kumari as well underline that employee involvement is creating an environment, in which people have an impact on decisions and actions that affect their jobs, moreover they believe that employee involvement has become a convenient catchall term to cover a variety of forms and organizational techniques. There are offered the examples of diverse forms as participative management, workplace democracy, representative participation, empowerment, quality circles, and employee ownership (Kumari & Kumari 2014). Some other scientists (Brown & Leigh 1996) suppose that work environment influences job involvement, and the characteristics as safety, support, meaning can increase the quality of job involvement in organization. Work environment is contextual, including organizational culture, which means that there is some obvious connection between job involvement and organizational culture.

Job Involvement and Organizational Culture Correlation Context

The relationship between organizational culture and employee job involvement can be explained social exchange theory (SET) perspective. According to the theory, as stated by Richard S Brenyah and Theresa Obuobisa-Darko, social behavior is the result of exchange process. When employees perceive the culture of the organization allows them to have good relationship with other members within the organization, where they have the needed support and power among others they tend to give their all, be dedicated and work with vigor (Brenyah & Obuobisa-Darko 2017). Anja Krog states the relationship of organizational culture and employee outcomes, which show that some cultures are more conducive to facilitating positive employee attitudes and behavior such as involvement than others; moreover, organizational culture in this research is viewed as a contextual variable, where some organizations provide their employees with more resources than others, depending on the characteristics or type of the existent culture (Krog 2014). According to Hobfoll (2001), different cultures types will have differing effects on job involvement. Some culture types will have a positive relationship with involvement, whereas other culture types will have a negative.

Some of the central characteristics of clan cultures are their focus on employee development, teamwork and collaboration, as well as trust in and commitment to employees (Cameron & Quinn 2006). Support, empowerment, and participation is key, therefore focus is put on fostering membership, affiliation, attachment and feelings of belongingness (Quinn & Kimberly 1984). Clan cultures actively offer job resources and create the tight connection and alignment of organizational and individual values, helping the employees to define their job involvement as positive.

Based on Cameron and Quinn (2006) research, adhocracy cultures have strong innovation, creativity, autonomy focus, they offer challenges and stimulate active search for fitting values among employees. Some experts underline that such a creativity focus help the employees to identify their job with growth, development and skills (Hartnell 2011). Development orientation in these cultures facilitate in employees the identification with their job, which means creating positive job involvement.

Hierarchy cultures are usually associated with rules, structure, procedures orientation, high level of efficiency and micro-management in the details how the job is done (Cameron & Quinn 2006). Hierarchy culture is based on the lack of autonomy and high level of control over employees' responsibilities and job tasks details. Employees are expected to work along with the standards and rules, stated by management, there are set power levels and efficient vertical linkages in communication. Hierarchy culture in this direction is less promoting positive job involvement, it underlines less importance of engagement and empowerment generally.

Market cultures state within the values competition and achievement, managers are usually demanding and focused on results. It is the culture with strong orientation on effectiveness in the meaning of achieving the goals and extending the standards (Cameron & Quinn 2006). Market cultures are highly achievement-oriented, goal-oriented and risk-taking, with the focus on aggressive performance (Hartnell 2011). Usually in these cultures there is a high level of stress, stressors become acute and create challenges in emotional labor, there is a chance of based on emotional dissonance behavioral deviations. Market cultures create less positive job involvement, more toxic in terms of high pressure and aggressiveness demands.

According to M. Rama Kumari and V. Lakshmi Prasanna Kumari, employee involvement is possible when the employees are more comfort with their job satisfaction, fringe benefits, motivational factors, empowerment and also flexible work schedules (Kumari & Kumari 2014). Employee involvement is more associated with the psychological identification with the organization, job involvement is more focused on the identification with the tasks and duties in symbolic and values way. So, organization culture definitely influences the extent of employee involvement, but how does it influence the positive or negative dimension of job involvement. For examples, employee can be highly professional and like the job very much identifying successes and life values with the mission, but disassociated with the organizational policies and values. The issue for the research is how the organizational culture can have the ability of foster job involvement of employees.

Conclusion

Job involvement is a psychologically-related attitude, it is the name of reflected identity of the employee's self-awareness of the job importance, how much is the fit of individual identity and job identity, as well as dimension of individual and organizational identity fit are realized in the organizational values, norms and artifacts. Job involvement intensity is correspondent to the correlation context created by the organizational culture type, some visible artifacts and norms accepted and promoted by managers. The future development of the theoretical and practical research is in the

following: how much is strong the influence of job involvement on organizational culture elements, and what is the cohesive primary sense, making the patters work strongly without conscious awareness.

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